

WOOD CONCRETE FOR HIGHT THERMAL EFFICIENCY COMPARE TO THE CONCRETE

Brougui Marwa

*Department of Wooden Constructions, Faculty of wood Engineering and Creative Industries,
University of Sopron, 9400 Sopron, Bajcsy-Zs. u. 4.Hungary, Marwa.Brougui@phd.uni-
sopron.hu.*

Szabó Péter

*Department of Wooden Constructions, Faculty of wood Engineering and Creative Industries,
University of Sopron, 9400 Sopron, Bajcsy-Zs. u. 4.Hungary,
szabo.peter@uni-sopron.hu*

Abstract

Construction materials play an important role in the energy performance of buildings in terms of energy demand. In order to reduce the energy consumption of buildings while achieving a certain level of comfort and thermal performance, it requires appropriate planning and design of the building's envelope. The development of new innovative materials such as wood concrete and the selection of building materials with favourable thermal properties have also played a crucial role in reaching this objective. In this paper, the thermal efficiency and performance of conventional concrete and wood concrete are compared based on the estimated energy consumption of a study building without thermal insulation. The literature review and simulation results show that conventional concrete is heavy, has a high amount of embodied energy, and relies heavily on non-renewable resources. In addition, conventional concrete has limited thermal performance and low heat storage capacity, which makes it less energy efficient than wood concrete, which has a high capacity to resist thermal variations and store heat relative to its weight; this heat storage helps to reduce heat loss from buildings. The low effusivity of wood concrete indicates their ability to slow heat transfer and quickly heat up at the surface by absorbing little heat, as well as their slow heat transfer rate. In contrast, the wood concrete study building consumes only 6427.29 [kJ/hour] of energy per year, which is 48.92% less than the concrete study building's 13137.26 [kJ/hour] of energy consumption per year. Wood concrete is a promising solution to the challenge of making the construction industry more sustainable in light of the economic and environmental challenges we face today. Its thermal and physical properties make it a perfect candidate for construction.

Keywords: Wood concrete, Energy efficiency, Sustainable material, Thermal performance, Concrete.

1. Introduction:

Construction is one of the major energy consumers, not only economically but also environmentally. The building sector represents 48% of the total energy consumed. Of these 48%, around 40% is intended for the operation of buildings (heating, air conditioning, lighting, IT, etc.), and around 8% is used for their construction (creation of materials, transport, and assembly) [1]. If the current trend continues, by 2050, the evolution of the field and the techniques of construction will make buildings the largest consumers of energy at the global level, using as much energy as the transport and industrial sectors combined [2].

The excessive use of non-renewable energy sources and the inefficient use of energy for heating and cooling buildings contribute to this problem, along with the high energy consumption associated with producing building materials such as concrete. Specifically,

cement concrete, which is the most produced and consumed type of concrete in the world, heavy and has negligible thermal resistance ($R = 1.15 \text{ m}^2\cdot\text{K}/\text{W}$ for a concrete block 20 cm thick) [3]. It also has high thermal inertia (2400 to 2610 $\text{kJ}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{K}$) [4]. Additionally, it uses largely non-renewable resources, is difficult to reuse, and has rather poor properties in terms of thermal insulation, storage heat capacity.

Reducing the building's energy consumption requires appropriate planning and design of the building envelope. In recent years, the passive concept of using eco-friendly building materials in new or renovated buildings has been developed to achieve this goal. Wood-concrete combines the best properties of concrete-cement and wood. The use of wood-concrete composites testifies to their energy efficiency as building materials. In addition to their fire resistance, this material offers great thermal performance due to the phase shift (the time it takes for heat to enter the house). The better the phase shift, the more comfortable the summer will be, providing good thermal insulation and limiting heat loss in winter, comparable to concrete. Moreover, it offers an effective response to the challenges of reducing CO_2 emissions with a negative carbon balance.

To expand the passive concept of using cost-effective and environmentally friendly building materials, wood-concrete, which reduces the impact of construction in terms of the use of non-renewable resources and building energy consumption, while achieving high levels of comfort and thermal performance compared to concrete, forms the objectives of our article.

2. Materials and methods:

The method consists of two parts:

Firstly, the study will provide a theoretical background by examining recent reviews and summaries of experimental studies. This background will help determine the composition of "wood concrete" and its thermal properties. Additionally, a comparative analysis of the thermal performance of wood concrete and traditional concrete will be conducted.

Secondly, an analytical approach will be presented, which includes two dynamic thermal simulations: one for a study case model and another for a model incorporating wood concrete as a building material, to compare their energy usage. The software "**Trnsys17**" will be utilized to analyse the thermal behaviour of a building, incorporating all its characteristics, such as heating systems, air conditioning, and location. The software will calculate the energy consumption and requirements of the building based on the construction materials used.

Download site: https://en.freedownloadmanager.org/userschoice/Download_Trnsys_17.html

▪ *Wood concrete :*

Wood-Concrete Composite (WCC) combines wood and cement to provide a sustainable construction solution. This material has primarily been used for finishing layers and insulation panels in the 20th century. However, recent developments aim to optimize its structural performance, energy efficiency, and ecological profiles by creating new lightweight structural concrete reinforced with wood or other light materials[5].

This composite material reduces energy consumption for heating and cooling systems and helps lower carbon emissions by replacing cement with wood in construction, unlike concrete [6]. Its performance depends on factors like component quantity, wood particle diameter, and cement type; different recipes can be used. Our study focuses on a specific recipe aligned with our objectives.

▪ *The components of wood concrete :*

The basic components are:

- 55% wood granulate,
- 38% cement,
- 7% water [7-8].

- *Wood granulate:*

It is characterized by a grain size of 8 mm to 10 mm and a length of about 20 mm to 35mm, and a thickness of 7 mm to 10 mm [8]. Wood particles replace stony aggregates in wood concrete. Deciduous tree wood may contain excess sugar, hindering cement hydration and concrete setting [9]. Mineralizing wood chips with lime or cement improves compatibility and strengthens the wood-cement composite [10].

- *Cement:*

The most recommended cement is CEM II/B-LL 32.5 R, a Portland limestone cement of the strength class 32.5 R according to EN 197-1, consisting of 72% clinker and 28% limestone [11]. In order to moderate, the ecological footprint of wood concrete, wood ash could be an effective alternative to cement. Based on the results obtained, the optimal replacement rate is about 30% by weight[13-6].

▪ *Wood-concrete mixtures:*

It has been observed that the mixing order significantly affects the rheological behaviour of the material. The selected mixing order is outlined in Table 1.

Table 1. Mixing sequence[12]

Step	Mixer Rotor Speed (rpm)	Cumulative Time (s)
1. Addition of cement and wood ash mix	140	0
2. Addition of water	140	60
3. Addition of wood particles	140	120
4. Change of speed	285	180
5. End of mixing	0	270

Air curing is normally done at room temperature or in an 80°C hydration oven and takes 14 to 28 days[12].

▪ *Thermal properties wood cement prepared as above vs. those of concrete:*

- *Thermal conductivity :*

Wood concrete offers a significant advantage due to its lighter weight compared to conventional concrete. This results its lower thermal conductivity, ranging from 0.09 to 0.016 W/(m·K) for a density of 600 or 700 kg/m³, depending on its composition [10] According to the recipe we studied, $\lambda= 0,0451 \text{ W/(m.K)}$ was found. In contrast, concrete typically has a thermal conductivity ranging from 0.1 to 0.7 W/(m·K) for a density of 2200–2400 kg/m³ [13]. Specifically, for a 19 cm block, the thermal conductivity of 0.678 W/(m·K) is measured [14].

- *Thermal resistance :*

Wood concrete is capable to withstand heat variations and offers thermal resistance, as high as R=3.07 m²·K/W for a 19 cm thick cinder block [15]. This value is approximately 2 to 3 times

higher than that of concrete, which has an R value of 0.280 m²·K/W for a 19 cm thick cinder block [14].

- *Specific heat :*

This property determines the material's ability to store heat. Effective heat storage can aid in reducing heat loss from buildings.

Table 2. Specific heat [16]

Materials	Specific heat (J.K ⁻¹ .kg ⁻¹)
Concrete	880 J.K ⁻¹ .kg ⁻¹
Wood concrete	1000.4 J.K ⁻¹ .kg ⁻¹

Table.2 shows that the specific heat value of wood concrete is higher (1000.4 J.K⁻¹.kg⁻¹) compared to ordinary concrete, which has a specific heat equal to 880 J.K⁻¹.kg⁻¹. The inclusion of wood chips in the mixture results in a significant enhancement (28%) of this property [16].

- *Thermal effusivity :*

This property demonstrates the materials' ability to absorb or release heat input at different rates. The low effusivity of wood concrete, measured to be 645 J/m².K⁻¹.s^{1/2} [16], indicates its capacity to slow down heat transfer. In contrast, concrete has a high heat absorption capacity, characterized by a strong effusivity of 2035J/m².K⁻¹.s^{1/2} [17].

- *Thermal diffusivity :*

It characterizes how heat spreads through a wall. Wood concrete has a lower thermal diffusivity of 0.189 10⁻⁶ m²/s [16], which results in a longer time for the heat front to cross the material's thickness, known as the phase shift, lasting 21 hours. On the other hand, concrete has a higher thermal diffusivity of 0.54 10⁻⁶ m²/s, resulting in a shorter phase shift ranging from 4 to 6 hours [18].

- *Hygrothermal behaviour:*

Wood concrete provides excellent hygrothermal regulation, absorbing and diffusing moisture for enhanced indoor comfort [19]. It also contributes to reducing negative CO₂ emissions by storing carbon dioxide [20]. It has a relative humidity range of 25% to 65%, while concrete maintains a relative humidity of 5%. Additionally, wood-concrete exhibits decreased thermal conductivity at relative humidity only above 65%, while concrete shows this effect at relative humidity levels greater than 5%[21].

▪ *Case study building parameter :*

- *Geological coordinates :*

Correspond to the city of Algiers, located in the North of Algeria. According to the current technical regulatory document in Algeria, the city falls under **climate zone A**; a hot, dry summer with a marked winter (the monthly average is never below 0°C).

- *Dimensions and 3D representation of the case study building :*

The case study building has a surface area of 306.85 m² and a height of 6.40 m (fig.1).

Figure 1: Case study building 3D
Source: Archicad.2023

The building's glazed surfaces account for about 13.67% of each façade and 20% of the floor area. Double glazed windows are used with heat transmission coefficient of $1.1 \text{ W/m}^2\cdot\text{K}$ and a solar factor of 0.65 (fig 2).

Figure 2: Case study building's main façade
Source: Archicad.2023

▪ *Thermal Characteristics of Materials:*

Case 01:

The building has 40 cm thick walls made of two layers of concrete blocks (B40), separated by expanded polystyrene; an air layer reinforces thermal insulation and prevents thermal bridging (Fig.3).

Figure 3: Case Study: Building Section - Construction Details
Source: Archicad.2023

The thermal conductivity and resistance values of the materials used in our case study are shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Thermal characteristics of building materials for exterior walls [14].

Material for masonry:	Thickness (m)	Thermal conductivity λ (W/m.k)	Thermal resistance R (m ² K/W)
Concrete block	0.19	0,678	0,280
expanded polystyrene	0.04	0.032	1.875

The same materials are used for both the floor and roof, but with different thicknesses, as shown in Figure 3.

Case 02:

In this case, the concrete blocks are replaced by wood concrete (19 cm thick blocks), without any thermal insulation as shown in figure 4.

Table 5 displays the thermal properties of the building material, indicating a thermal conductivity value of 0.045(W/m.k) for wood concrete.

Table 5. Thermal characteristics of construction materials for separation walls [13].

Material for Masonry :	Thickness (m)	Thermal conductivity λ (W/m.k)	Thermal resistance R (m ² K/W)
Wood concrete block	0.19	0.0451	4.21

Figure 4: Case Study: Building Section - Construction Details
Source: Archicad.2023

3. Results and discussion:

In this step, the 'TRNSYS.17' software is configured with the building dimensions and thermal data for both cases. The 'TRNBUILD' module (Type 56) factors in the building's orientation, window locations, glazing type, and the thicknesses of walls and floor layers with their respective thermal conductivity values from Table 4 and Table 5. It also takes into account all heat gains, including the number of occupants (4 people) and the power of electrical devices. The calculation step is set to one year, equivalent to 8760 hours.

The simulation results are obtained for two distinct periods:

- Winter period: 4039 hours (5 months).
- Summer period: 2350 hours (3 months + 22 days).

To reach a favourable ambient temperature of 18C° in winter, and 23C° in summer, a specific heating and cooling power of 100W/m² was installed.

3.1 Amount of energy consumed:

In the first case, the simulation results reveal that during the winter, our building of 306.85 m² surface area takes an average power of 7638.47 [kJ/hour] for heating and 5498.79 [kJ/hour] for cooling during the summer.

According to figure 5, we have observed that the highest power consumption value in the building is 20.000 kJ/h.

Figure 5: The course of power consumption over a year for concrete building.
Source: TRNSYS.17.2023

In the second case, the simulation results indicated that by using wood concrete instead of concrete, and without any thermal insulation in the building, the energy consumption required to maintain the ideal ambient temperature during both summer and winter decreased to 4612.51[kJ/hour] for heating, and 1814.78 [kJ/hour] for cooling. Additionally, the building's highest energy consumption value is recorded as 16,000 kJ/h (fig.6).

Figure 6: The course of power consumption over a year for wood-concrete building.
Source: TRNSYS.17.2023

In order to determine the amount of energy consumption for the building, the "ISO 13790" standard for Energy Performance of Buildings - Calculation of Energy Use for Space Heating and Cooling utilizes the following equation:

$$\text{Energy Consumption (kJ/a)} = \text{Power Consumption (kJ)} \times \text{Duration of Use (a)} \quad [22].$$

The concrete reference building equipped with thermal insulation consumes an average of 30,851,901.5 kJ per year for heating and 12922650 kJ per year for cooling the building. In contrast, the wooden concrete building without thermal insulation uses an average energy of only 18629887.5 kJ per year for heating and 4265250 kJ per year for cooling (fig.7).

**Figure 7: The winter and summer energy consumption of the buildings [kJ/a].
Source: Author 2023**

The results obtained in our study are attributed to the excellent thermal properties of wood concrete. In particular, its low thermal conductivity (0.045 W/m·K) and ability to regulate indoor temperatures through phase shift are responsible for the significant energy savings observed.

4. Conclusion:

Building materials are an important factor in the energy performance of buildings. From the point of view of energy demand, the manufacture and exploitation of building materials requires an enormous amount of energy, not only in the construction phase but also in all phases of their existence.

In summary, choosing building materials with good thermal properties can reduce energy consumption. Wood concrete is a sustainable material with high thermal efficiency and performance. As shown by our study, a building made of wood concrete without thermal insulation **consumes 47.70% less energy annually** than an insulated concrete building. Moreover, this result is thanks to the high performance and thermal efficiency of wood concrete:

- Low thermal conductivity ; $0.09 \text{ W/m.k} \leq 0.678 \text{ W/m.k}$ (ordinary concrete)
- High capacity resisted heat variations; $2.90 \text{ m}^2.\text{k/W} \geq 0.28 \text{ m}^2.\text{k/W}$ (ordinary concrete).
- Ability to delay warm up ; $645 \text{ J/m}^{-2}.\text{K}^{-1}.\text{s}^{1/2} \leq 2035 \text{ J/m}^{-2}.\text{K}^{-1}.\text{s}^{1/2}$ (ordinary concrete)

- A large capacity to regulate the indoor thermal environment offered by the phase shift (the time to let outside heat inside the house); 21 hours \geq concrete varies between 4 and 6 hours.
- High capacity to conserve heat; $100.4 \text{ J.K}^{-1}.\text{kg}^{-1} \geq 880 \text{ J.K}^{-1}.\text{kg}^{-1}$ (ordinary concrete).

Therefore, using sustainable materials like wood concrete can lead to more energy-efficient and environmentally friendly buildings.

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